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CRISPER-Cas System, A Molecular Miracle, Enhancing the Yield and Pest Resistance in Crop Improvement (A Review)

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ABSTRACT

In this era of growing global population, advancement and increased demand of varieties in food and crop industry is not an easy task. Nowadays feeding such a growing population while protecting crops from disease and loss is one of the most urgent challenges of our time. Traditional methods of breeding has contributed significantly, but in this age of growing globalization, consumerism, commercialization along with easy access to different crops, food culture and dietary practices demand for different and local crops has been increased.

According to an article published in Nature food the total global food demand is expected to rise by 35% to 56% between 2010 and 2050 and the population at risk of hunger is expected to change by 91% to +8% over the same period (Michel Van *et al.*, 2021). The probable reasons are also climate stresses such as climate change, soil degradation and emerging pathogens threaten the yield in ways that conventional breeding alone cannot overcome. In this new age new edge technology also required. CRISPER/Cas genome editing technique offers scientists a remarkable level of precision and allow flexible reshaping of crop traits according to desired need. This paper brings together recent advances in using CRISPER to enhance yield and engineer disease resistance, in this review you will find promising case studies field research and laboratory and highlights the evolving regulatory social and commercial contexts. And the most important part it outlines those directions for research that can bridge the gap between scientific innovation and sustainable agriculture and industry. CRISPER/Cas genome editing has revolutionaries crop improvement, offering efficient, precise and flexible tools that can modify plant genomes which enables targeted edits in desired yield related genes while also allowing knockout or fine-tuning of potential genes to enhance disease resistance. Finally in summary this paper reviews integrating laboratory, greenhouse, recent breakthroughs and field research discussing molecular mechanisms, regulatory landscapes, public perception, challenges in this field and future perspective.

Keywords: CRISPER Cas9, Cas12a, crop improvement, yield enhancement, disease resistance, gene editing, molecular tools.

Introduction

The global food system is now facing immense pressure as population growth, urbanization, and climate change converge to challenge agricultural productivity and food security in various areas of the world. In this scenario FAO predicts in its report that a 50% increase in food production is required by 2050. According to some of these reports in 2025 the world is addressing high food price (inflation). SOFI 2025 report presents the new data and analysis on global hunger, food security and nutrition worldwide which also includes updated estimates on the cost and affordability of healthy diets. It is reported that in 2024 that 8.2% of the world's population (673 million) experienced hunger, down from 8.5% in 2023. Hunger remains above pre-Covid-19 levels which is indicating incomplete recovery. It has also been estimated that by 2030, almost 512 million people may remain chronically undernourished because of this raising demand and supply mismatch, with nearly 60% people in hunger solely in Africa. For achieving SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) we will need major shifts in policy, funding, and food systems and food variety production. There are a lot of such hunger and inflation related data and predictions by various organizations. The major contributors of these circumstances are climate change related problems like drought, floods, heat waves, and altered rainfall patterns all these are negatively impacting crops which lead to food security issues in many areas of the world. Pathogens (disease causing organisms) and pests have adapted or emerged, causing 20-40% annual crop losses globally. Traditional breeding and hybridization techniques exemplified by the green revolution, improved yield and tools for food security but are constrained by long cycles, low efficiency for polygenic traits, and reliance on natural variation. These problems demand extensive modern molecular tools in which favourable genomic manipulations can be done to solve the problem from the root or base. For this particularly CRISPER/Cas (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats) systems, allow precise genome modifications, enabling strategies such as susceptibility gene knockout, promoter editing, and multiplexed edits, with higher public acceptance due to their mimicry of natural mutations. CRISPER Cas9 is in fact a natural genome editing process which is used by bacteria as its own immune defense mechanism in which when the bacteria got infected by a virus' DNA the bacteria capture small pieces of virus genome and incorporate it into its own DNA in a particular pattern so that it can create segments called CRISPER arrays. This way the bacteria remember the viruses (or closely related ones). When next time the virus attacks the bacteria produces RNA segments from the incorporated CRISPER arrays that recognize and attach to the foreign DNA (virus DNA) then the bacteria use Cas9 or similar type of enzymes to cut the DNA apart, which disables the virus. Researchers use this machinery to edit DNA. In this machinery small piece of RNA with a short sequence known as "guide" sequence binds to a specific target sequence in a cell's DNA, much like the RNA segments which bacteria produce from the CRISPER array. This specific RNA called as guide RNA attaches to the Cas9 enzyme. When it is introduced into the target cells, it recognizes the desired specific DNA sequence and the Cas9 enzyme cuts the DNA at that targeted location which is a type of mirroring the process in bacteria. Despite the fact that Cas9 is the enzyme that can edit genomes in a range of species which includes prokaryotes as well as eukaryotes for example yeast (*S.cerevisiae*), *C.albicans*, zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), fruit fly (*Drosophila melanogaster*), ants (*Harpegnathos saltator* and *Ooceraea biroii*),

mosquitoes (aedes aegypti), nematodes, plants, mice and monkeys. More technically in this system Cas9 which is an RNA dependant DNA endonuclease (enzymes that can cut DNA internally on specific sequences) which is associated with the CRISPER adaptive immune system. Apart from its original function of immunity in different bacterial species it has been also used as a genetic engineering tool to perform site-directed double-strand breaks in DNA chain. These breaks can help in gene modification by either activating the gene or the introduction of heterologous genes through non-homologous end joining (a type of recombination mechanism between different type of genes) and homologous recombination respectively in desired model organisms., en.wikipedia.org. In this way this technology can be used in agriculture to tackle present day problems of food and hunger where selective breeding can be done, in selective breeding breeders identify rare or important plant variants with desired qualities then they can breed these plants and their progenies to increase the recurrence of the trait in the population.

The CRISPER/Cas system consists of two parts-

1. CRISPER (Clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats)
2. Cas (CRISPER associated proteins)

1. CRISPER/Cas system: Molecular working mechanisms

CRISPER is consists of highly conserved short repeated sequences separated by spacer sequences which are of same size as the crisper sequence. The size of these repeats can varies between 23-47 base pairs and 21-72 base pairs, respectively. The spacers are unique sequences which are used as recognition elements. Another feature associated with the CRISPER loci is the presence of a conserved sequence, called leader sequence, located upstream of the CRISPER with respect to the direction of transcription. CRISPER working requires a set of CRISPER-associated (Cas) gene, usually found adjacent to the CRISPER, that code for Cas proteins essential to the immune response. Cas proteins can perform different functions of nucleases, helicases and polymerases. The CRISPER-Cas systems currently works through the cooperation of many different types of Cas proteins resulting in this system currently being grouped into two classes, six types, and over 30 subtypes.

Figure 1- Locus Organization: CRISPER loci consist of 23 to 27 bp palindromic repeat sequences, the spacer has no common feature in their sequences. (The Cas gene is located close to the CRISPER loci.)

A CRISPER locus is a region containing repeats and spacers. Repeats are short, palindromic DNA sequences and spacers are unique DNA fragments derived from past viral infections. Spacers act like molecular memory of previous invaders. Cas genes encode CRISPER-associated proteins their functions include spacer acquisition, crRNA processing, and DNA cleavage some examples are Cas1, Cas2, Cas9, Cas12, Cas13 (different types have different targets: DNA or RNA). The mechanism has three main stages the first stage is adaptation (Spacer acquisition) when a virus infects the cell, Cas1-Cas2 complex recognizes foreign DNA, a small fragment of the viral DNA (protospacer) is excised. This fragment is integrated into the CRISPER locus as a new spacer. It becomes part of the bacterial immune memory. Bacteria record a part of the virus genome to recognize it in the future. Stage 2 is the maturation phase of crRNA and its expression. The CRISPER locus (repeats + spacer) is transcribed into a long precursor RNA: **pre-crRNA** and is processed by Cas proteins or RNases to produce short crRNAs. Another RNA (tracrRNA) pairs with pre-crRNA to form a functional guide RNA for Cas9 system. The immune memory is converted into guide RNAs that can scan for matching viral DNA. In the third stage targeted cleavage happens this also called Interference here the crRNA assembles with the appropriate Cas protein (e.g., Cas9). This forms an **effector complex** that scans incoming DNA for a complementary sequence, recognition often requires a short sequence near the target called PAM (Protospacer Adjacent Motif), when the target DNA and crRNA match, Cas protein cleavage the foreign DNA. The viral genome is destroyed and infection is stopped. CRISPR-Cas works like a guided nuclease that can cut the invader DNA with sequence specificity. The CRISPR-Cas system posses an adaptive immune approach which is implemented by bacteria and archaea to protect against pathogenic genetic elements such as plasmids and bacteriophages. This defence system depends on the combined action of a CRISPR gene locus and an array of CRISPR-associated (Cas) proteins. Together, these components enable the organism to capture fragments of foreign DNA, convert them into heritable immune memory, and subsequently mount sequence-specific degradation of the same or related invaders upon reinfection. Owing to its programmability and precision, the CRISPR-Cas machinery has also become a foundational tool in molecular biology and genome engineering.

Fig 2: guideRNA made up of crRNA and tracrRNA and Cas9 protein.(Courtesy:-google images)

Fig 3- CRISPER working mechanism, courtesy:- Zulqurnain khan, An Outlook on Global Regulatory Landscape for Genome-Edited Crops, October 2021

2. CRISPER/Cas system in Plants:

The progress of CRISPR-Cas genome editing technology has presented a groundbreaking and precise method for genetic alteration and accelerating the focused adaptations of plant genomes to gain desired characteristics. Different crops varieties has been enhanced or improved gene editing using crisper technology. Below are some examples of such crops.

Table 1: Examples of gene-edited crop species by CRISPR/Cas9 system.

Crops in Six Categories	Species
a. Feed Crops- <i>Alfalfa</i>	
b. Fiber Crops- <i>Cotton</i>	
c. Edible/food Crops -	<i>Banana, apple, basil, blueberry, cabbage, carrot, cassava, chickpea, chill, citrus, coconut, cowpea, cucumber, date palm, grapefruit, grapes, kale, kiwifruit, lactuca sativa, lemon, lettuce, lychee, maize, melon, oats, pepper, pear, papaya, orange, potato, rice, pumpkin, saffron, strawberry, sugar beet, sweet potato, tomato, watermelon, wheat, yam</i>
Crops in Six Categories	Species
d. Industrial Use crops-	<i>Cichorium, coffee, dandelion, hevea brasiliensis, jatropha curcas, millet, papaver, parasponia, salvia miltiorrhiza, sorghum, sugarcane, switchgrass, tragopogon, tripterygium, wilfordii</i>
e. Oli crops-	<i>canola, flax, oil palm, oilseed rape, soybean, sunflower</i>
f. Ornamental crops-	<i>lily, lotus, petunia, poplar, rose, sedum, snapdragon, torenia</i>

(Courtesy – Leu et al., 2021)

Table 2 -Examples of some applications on crop quality improvement by using crisper/cas9 technology.**Part A**

Applications	Crops	Editing effector	Target gene	Associated trait	References
1. Improving the Crop Physical Appearance	1. Rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>)	CRISPER-Cas9	GS3	Increased grain length	Usman <i>et al.</i> , 2021; DOI: 10.3390/ijms22063225 MDPI
	2. Rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>)	CRISPER-Cas9	GW2, GW5, GW6	Increased grain weight	Xu <i>et al.</i> , 2016 (commonly cited; part of peer-reviewed tables) PeerJ
	3. Wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i>)	CRISPER-Cas9	TaGW7	Increased grain width and weight	Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Ren <i>et al.</i> , 2025 (wheat GS3 info) PeerJ+1
	4. Tomato	CRISPER-Cas9	OVATE, CLV, fas, lc, ENO	Modified fruit shape and size	PMC
	5. Groundcherry (<i>Physalis spp.</i>)	CRISPR-Cas9	CLV1	Increased fruit size	Lemmon <i>et al.</i> , 2018 (summarized in review) PeerJ

Color Modification	Tomato (<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>)	CRISPR-Cas9	Multiple carotenoid pathway genes	Increased lycopene content	Li <i>et al.</i> , 2018; <i>Frontiers in Plant Sci.</i> DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2018.00559 American Chemical Society publications
	Tomato	CRISPR-Cas9	<i>SILCYe</i> , <i>SIBCH</i>	Increased β -carotene	Study (Biofortification) 2025, Elsevier (PubMed) PubMed
	Banana	CRISPR-Cas9	<i>LCYe</i>	Enhanced β -carotene	Kaur <i>et al.</i> , 2020; PubMed PMID: 32006663 PubMed
3. Improving crop texture quality & Prolonging shelf Life	Strawberry (Fragaria × ananassa)	CRISPR-Cas9	FaPG1	Increased firmness & shelf life	Edit by Chinese group; PubMed PMID: 36960432 PubMed
	Tomato	CRISPR-Cas9	SLPG	Reduced fruit softening	Front. Plant Sci. (mutagenesis study)

Table 2. Part B

4. Biofortification of nutrient elements	Tomato	CRISPER-Cas9	Carotenoid pathway genes	Higher lycopene (appearance/nutrition)	Li X. <i>et al.</i> , 2018; DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2018.00559
		CRISPER-Cas9	<i>SILCYe</i> , <i>SIBCH</i>	Higher β -carotene	Elsevier (PubMed 2025)
		CRISPER-Cas9	<i>LCYe</i>	β -carotene increase (~6-fold)	Kaur <i>et al.</i> , 2020; PubMed PMID: 32006663
5. Increasing γ-Aminobutyric Acid (GABA) Content	Tomato	CRISPER-Cas9	Deletion of GAD auto-inhibitory region	Increased GABA (~7 \times)	Reported in review (MDPI) — SIGAD editing
	Tomato	CRISPER-Cas9	<i>SIGABA-TPs</i> , <i>SICAT9</i> , <i>SISSADH</i>	GABA increased ~20 \times (multiple targets)	Li <i>et al.</i> (multiplex), specifics in review
	Rice	CRISPER-Cas9	<i>OsGAD3</i>	Increased GABA (~7 \times)	Akama <i>et al.</i> 2020 (cited in cereal review)
6. Biofortification of micronutrients and amino acids	wheat	CRISPER-Cas9	α -gliadin family	Lower gluten (reduced allergen)	Sánchez-León <i>et al.</i> , 2018 DOI: 10.1105/tpc.18.00201
	Rice	CRISPER editing (general)	Lys biosynthesis genes <i>AK</i> , <i>dapA</i>	Increased lysine	Zhu <i>et al.</i> , 2019 DOI: 10.1016/j.cj.2019.03.001
7. Improving fatty acid composition	Soybean	CRISPER-Cas12a	<i>FAD2-1A</i> & <i>FAD2-1B</i>	Higher oleic acid	Al Amin <i>et al.</i> , 2019 DOI: 10.1016/j.plantsci.2019.11.0198
	Soybean	CRISPER-Cas9	<i>GmFATB1</i>	Lower saturated fats	Don <i>et al.</i> , 2019 DOI: 10.1016/j.plantsci.2019.11.0210
8. Eliminating anti-nutrients	Wheat	CRISPER-Cas9	α -gliadin region	Reduced gluten anti-nutrient	Jouanin <i>et al.</i> , 2020: 10.3389/fpls.2020.00338
	Soybean	CRISPER-Cas9	KT11 & KT13	Reduced trypsin inhibitor	Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2020: 10.1016/j.tifs.2020.01.006

3. Engineering the Cas9 endonuclease

All the applications of CRISPER technology is only possible after the desired modification of cas proteins which is also known as engineering of cas9 endonuclease protein. For a specific CRISPER-Cas experiment it is important to choose both the gRNA and the Cas9 enzyme. But in reality, inside a cell's genome most gRNA targeting sequences will have extra sites of partial homology in whole genome, which are known as off-targets and these can impact the experiment. For ideal gRNA targeting the gRNA sequence should have perfect homology to the target DNA and no homology anywhere in the genome. There are some online software available ([gRNA Design Software](#)) which can help in selecting an optimized gRNA for the experiment. With the optimized gRNA an engineered Cas9 is ideal for enhanced working of the CRISPER-Cas system with desired specificity. From *streptococcus pyogenes* an enzyme spCas9 has been engineered into various versions for specific applications hence it is the most popular engineered Cas9, it has also reduced the dependency on specific PAM sequences and the formation of new tools.

4. Method for Cas9 engineering

Among various techniques used for cas9 engineering one of the popular methods is the **structure-guided protein engineering or mutagenesis**, where amino acid residues are modified according to the Cas9-DNA crystal structures, in this method mutations are introduced to the DNA binding interfaces or mainly in the PAM interacting domain to change PAM recognition sequences or reduce nonspecific DNA interactions. Outcomes of this method are improved specificity (e.g., eSpCas9, SpCas9-HF1) and enhanced PAM compatibility (e.g., Cas9-NG) (Nishimasu *et al.*, 2014). Another technique is **directed evolution** as the name suggests it involves repeated cycles of random mutagenesis which is followed by selection of desired properties such as wide-ranging PAM recognition or enhanced specificity. Some Cas9 variants made by this technique are xCas9 (NG, GAA, GAT) they show improved and balanced editing efficiency and specificity. (Hu *et al.*, 2018). **Domain inactivation** is a catalytic

Fig 4 A- Pie representation showing crop quality improvement (courtesy- Leu *et al.*,2021)

Fig 4 B-graph showing crop quality improvement (courtesy – leu et al.,2021)

Engineering technique which use targeted mutation of Cas9 domains, HNH and RuvC that enables precise control on cleavage activity of DNA (Ran *et al.*, 2013). When one nuclease domain is inactivate it performs single-strand break this modified Cas9 is termed as **nickase Cas9 (nCas9)** (Satomura *et al.*, 2017).When both domains of Cas9 have inactivated then it is termed as dead **Cas9 (dCas9)** (Qi *et al.*, 2013), these engineered Cas9 systems reduces genomic damage and provide a platform for base editing and transcriptional regulation (Gilbert *et al.*, 2013).Sometimes Cas9 is engineered by fusing it with functional domains such as deaminases for base editing , transcriptional regulators by activation or repression and DNA repair modulators, all these produces outcomes such as base editors (CBE, ABE) enabling precise nucleotide substitutions and editing without double-strand breaks, this method is known as **fusion protein engineering** . There is another engineering called Rational optimization for plant system in which cas9 proteins are further optimized for utilization of plants as codon optimization, addition of nuclear localization signals (NLS) and removal of unnecessary bacterial domains. Enhanced nuclear targeting and increased editing efficiency in crop genomes are the outcomes.

Fig 5: Formation of engineered RNP complex and Double strand repair via NHEJ or HDR. (Courtesy: Zulqurnain Khan *et al.*2021)

5. Increasing fidelity of Cas9: -

Currently there is no defined measure of fidelity so sometimes in Crisper cas9 system it is referred to as increased capacity of specific targeting. The precision is increased by researchers by engineering Cas9 into high fidelity Cas9s (**hfCas9**). hfCas9s were made by mutating specific amino acid residues to reduce less accurate target editing. These mutations are nearly random where some can disrupt interaction between Cas9 and DNA strand, while others work to increase Cas9's proofreading powers. No matter what the method is, high fidelity enzymes perform less off-target editing than wild type Cas9 enzymes.

Table 3: Examples of high fidelity Cas9 enzymes with their specific targeting

Enzyme	Specific target
1. eSpCas9(1.1)	weaken interactions between the HNH/RuvC groove and the non- target DNA strand
2. SpCas9-HF1	Disrupt cas9's interactions with DNA phosphate backbone
3. HypaCas9	Increase Cas9 proofreading and discrimination
4. evoCas9	decrease off-target effects
5. xCas9 3.7	mutations in multiple domains to expand PAM recognition, increase specificity, and decrease off-target effects
6. Sniper-Cas9	less off-target activity; compatible with truncated gRNAs to increase specificity
7. SuperFi-Cas9	Increases fidelity with reduced nuclease activity

6. Increasing Cas9 PAM flexibility

CRISPER systems are designed to make more precise editing which require PAM sequences in for high precision editing in close proximity regions. These PAM sequences are abundant throughout the human genome but this may not be positioned exactly where your desired target gene is. Engineered SpCas9 enzymes which are altered in the PAM sequence are available which are known as PAM-flexible or PAMless Cas9s.

Table4: PAMless Cas9 system and its examples along with specific functions

PAMless Cas9	Function
1. <i>xCas9</i>	NG, GAA, and GAT; increased nuclease fidelity
2. <i>spCas9-NG</i>	NG; increased in vitro activity
3. <i>SpG</i>	NGN; increased in vitro activity
4. <i>SpRY</i>	NRN/NYN, where R = A or G, Y=C or T
5. <i>SpRYc</i>	SpRY PAMs plus NNG; a chimeric version of SpRY

7. Anti-CRISPER

Long duration of Cas9 activity can increase the risk of off-target cleavage or cytotoxicity, but Acr (Anti-CRISPER) proteins can help control CRISPER activity naturally. Acr proteins are evolved in mobile genetic elements like phages to overcome the CRISPER systems that archaea and bacteria use to protect against these foreign RNA/DNA. Acr family members achieve this capacity of inhibiting CRISPER by various mechanisms, including Cas9's endonuclease domain inhibition, blocking crRNA loading or PAM recognition, or Cas9 protein degradation. Mostly Acr proteins are specific for specific type of Cas9 enzyme, e.g., Cas9 or Cas12a. These are identified by their names for example CRISPER type II cas9 proteins are inhibited by AcrII and AcrV inhibits CRISPER type V Cas12a systems. In some rare cases Acr can work with multiple types, such as AcrVA3.1, which can inhibit both Cas12a and Cas3. Some species of CRISPER enzyme has particular Acr proteins, such as AcrIIA7-10, which inhibits SpCas9. More commonly, AcrA2 and AcrA4, isolated from *Listeria monocytogenes* inhibits multiple species of Cas enzymes for example both LmoCas9 and SpCas9. Acr proteins helps in control both when and where genome editing happens. CASANOVA, developed by Dominik Niopek's lab, is a way to control genome editing optogenetically by fusing the anti-CRISPER protein AcrIIA4 with the photosensitive LOV2 domain. Several labs have also developed specific miRNAs with endogenous cell-types to control Acr activity for restricting CRISPER editing only to the target tissue.

8. Precise Modifications by Homology Directed Repair (HDR)

CRISPR has the ability to make small, highly precise edits of a handful of bases, or even a single base. These small precision edits can be done by HDR, base editing, and prime editing, and are regularly used to alter an amino acid, turn a promoter on/off, or addition of small protein tags. HDR creates specific genomic edits by copying from a DNA **donor template**. The donor template contains the desired sequence and is delivered to the cell along with the gRNA(s) and Cas enzyme. The donor DNA contains the desired edit as well as additional DNA matching the sequence immediately upstream and downstream of the target site (termed left and right homology arms). The length of each homology arm depends on the size of the change being introduced; larger insertions require longer homology arms.

9. CRISPER for disease resistance

CRISPR-Cas genome editing has come in lights in recent years and is utilised as revolutionary tool for engineering disease resistance in plants by inducing and enabling precise, aimed modification in host susceptibility genes and immunologic regulatory pathways (Wang *et al.*, 2014). CRISPR is a preferred tool as it allows quick development of resistant varieties without making the DNA chimeric or impure, unlike the conventional breeding methods, which is cumbersome and time-consuming process and also it is constrained by the available genetic diversities (Zaidi *et al.*, 2016). By knocking out specific genes that are susceptible such as *MLO* gene in Wheat, or *SWEET* gene in rice, the plants exhibit improved resistance against powdery mildew caused by fungus and bacterial blight of rice caused by *Xanthomonas* (Wang *et al.*, 2014). CRISPR has also been known to target viral genomes directly, providing resistance against the Deoxy Vira such as Gemini viruses in the crops such as Cassava and tomatoes (Nekrasov *et al.*, 2017; Tripathi *et al.*, 2019). CRISPR licence the multiplex editing, allowing contemporaneous modifications of numerous genes to achieve broader spectrum and long- lasting resistance (Zaidi *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, CRISPR- based resistance to disease empowers sustainable agriculture by decreasing the reliance on chemical pesticides and in turn lowering the harmful effects on environment. This also improves crop yield stability under biotic stress

(Zaidi *et al.*, 2016). In several countries, with magnifying regulatory acceptance crops that are genetically edited, CRISPR turns out to be a promising tool for ensuring food security and climate resilience in agriculture in decades to follow (Zaidi *et al.*, 2016).

Table no.5- Disease resistance in plants by CRISPER system

Plant Species	Target Gene / Region	Pathogen / Disease	CRISPR Strategy	Result	Reference
Rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>)	<i>OsSWEET11/13/14</i>	Bacterial blight (<i>Xanthomonas oryzae</i>)	Promoter editing / knockout	High resistance	Li <i>et al.</i> , 2012
Wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i>)	<i>TaMLO</i>	Powdery mildew	Gene knockout	Durable resistance	Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2014
Tomato (<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>)	Viral genome	Tomato yellow leaf curl virus	CRISPR- mediated viral targeting	Reduced viral load	Nekrasov <i>et al.</i> , 2017
Cassava (<i>Manihot esculenta</i>)	Viral DNA	Cassava mosaic disease	CRISPR interference	Virus resistance	Tripathi <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Arabidopsis thaliana	<i>DMR6</i>	Bacterial & fungal pathogens	Gene knockout	Broad- spectrum resistance	De Toledo Thomazella <i>et al.</i> , 2021
Grapevine (<i>Vitis vinifera</i>)	<i>MLO</i>	Powdery mildew	Targeted mutagenesis	Increased resistance	Wan <i>et al.</i> , 2020

10. Delivery of CRISPR Components in Plants

Effective delivery of CRISPR–Cas system components into plant cells is an important aspect of successful and desired genome editing. The delivery strategy has key impacts on transformation efficiency, tissue specificity, mutation heritability, and regulatory classification of edited crops (Altpeter *et al.*, 2016; Maher *et al.*, 2020). Some of the physical and biological CRISPER delivery methods have been developed to enter Cas nucleases and guide RNAs into

plant cells, each possessing unique advantages and disadvantages depending on the crop species and the experimental objectives (Liu *et al.*, 2021).

10 (a.) Agrobacterium-mediated Transformation

Agrobacterium tumefaciens-mediated transformation method is the most widely used approach for introducing CRISPR–Cas systems construct into plant genomes. This method comprises, T-DNA carrying Cas nuclease and guide RNA expression cassettes that are transferred into plant cells and securely integrated into the host genome which enables heritable genome modifications (Hwang *et al.*, 2013; Shan *et al.*, 2014). This system has been greatly applied in dicot crops such as tomato and soybean and has also been upgraded for monocot crops including rice and maize (Xie and Yang, 2013; Zhang *et al.*, 2014). Tissue-specific or inducible promoters allows the use of controlled expression of CRISPR components, and multiplex genome editing can be attained by introducing multiple guide RNAs in a single construct (Ma *et al.*, 2015). Though the integration of foreign DNA classifies such plants as transgenic which necessitates segregation of the transgene in subsequent generations to obtain non-transgenic edited lines (Chen *et al.*, 2019).

Table 6: Agrobacterium mediated crisper delivery system, example crops and results

Crop	Target gene(s)	Delivery technique	Modified trait	Key results	Reference
Rice	<i>OsSWEET14</i>	Agrobacterium and Cas9	Bacterial blight invulnerability	Enhanced disease resistance	Li <i>et al.</i> , 2012
Tomato	<i>SLAGO7</i>	Agrobacterium and Cas9	Development of leaf	Stable heritable mutation	Brooks <i>et al.</i> , 2014
Wheat	<i>TaMLO</i>	Agrobacterium and Cas9	Powdery mildew resistance	Disease-resistant plants	Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2014
Soybean	<i>GmFT2a</i>	Agrobacterium and Cas9	Flowering time	Altered flowering phenotype	Cai <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Maize	<i>ZmIPK1</i>	Agrobacterium and Cas9	Reduced phytic acid	Improved nutritional quality	Feng <i>et al.</i> , 2016

10 (b.) Particle Bombardment (Biolistic Delivery)

Particle bombardment provides the capability of physical delivery of CRISPR–Cas reagents into plant tissues by enhancing DNA-, RNA-, or protein-coated microprojectiles into the target cells. This approach is specifically useful for crops that are recalcitrant to Agrobacterium infection such as wheat and maize (Svitashev *et al.*, 2016; Liang *et al.*, 2017). Biolistic delivery allows direct transformation of the embryogenic calli and meristematic tissues without being relied on biological vectors (Altpeter *et al.*, 2016). Although, this technique often results in multiple copy insertions, random genomic integration, and cellular damage, which can complicate the stable line development and genomic integrity (Liu *et al.*, 2021). Recent enhancements in delivery parameters and reagent dosage have increased editing efficiency and reduced unwanted insertions (Svitashev *et al.*, 2016).

Table 7. Examples of few particle bombardment delivery uses

10(c.)	Crops	Target gene(s)	Delivery technique	Modified trait	Key results	Reference
	Maize	<i>ZmALS2</i>	Biolytic and Cas9 plasmid	Herbicide resistance/safety	Targeted mutation with precisions	Svitashev et al., 2015
	Wheat	<i>TaGW2</i>	Biolytic and Cas9	Size of the grain	Grain weight increase	Liang et al., 2017
	Barley	<i>HvPM19</i>	Biolytic and Cas9	Seed dormancy	Changed dormancy	Lawrenson et al., 2015
	Rice	<i>OsBADH2</i>	Biolytic and Cas9	Fragrance or aroma	Rice produced with characteristic aroma	Shan et al., 2015
	Sorghum	<i>SbPDS</i>	Biolytic and Cas9	Specific albino marker	Feasibility study	Che et al., 2018

Protoplast Transfection

Protoplast transfection is involving the introduction of CRISPR–Cas components into plant cells which lack cell walls, typically using polyethylene glycol (PEG) or electroporation. This technique allows rapid uptake of plasmid DNA, mRNA, or ribonucleoprotein complexes and is popularly used for testing guide RNA efficiency and functional genomics studies (Woo *et al.*, 2015; Lin *et al.*, 2018). Protoplast-based delivery provides transient expression of CRISPR components without secure genomic integration and thereby minimizing regulatory constraints (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Despite these advantages the regeneration of whole plants from edited protoplasts remains technically challenging in many crop species which limits large-scale agricultural application (Altpeter *et al.*, 2016).

Table 8. Examples of protoplast mediated delivery in some plants

Crop	Target genes	Delivery technique	Modified trait	Key results	Reference
Arabidopsis	<i>AtPDS3</i>	PEG-protoplast and Cas9	Albino phenotype	Enhanced transitory editing	Lin et al., 2018
Rice	<i>OsROC5</i>	PEG-protoplast and Cas9	Rolling in leaf	Useful validation	Zhang et al., 2014
Tomato	<i>SIPDS</i>	PEG-protoplast and Cas9	Albino phenotype	Quick gRNA testing	Kim et al., 2017
Tobacco	<i>NtPDS</i>	PEG-protoplast and Cas9	Albino phenotype	Increased editing efficiency	Woo et al., 2015
Maize	<i>ZmHKT1</i>	PEG-protoplast and Cas9	Salt tolerance	Useful gene study	Liang et al., 2014

10(d.) Virus-based Deliver

Virus-mediated delivery methods utilize engineered plant viruses for the transport guide RNAs or CRISPR–Cas components into the host tissues. This approach makes use of the natural infectivity and systemic movement of viruses to persuade genome editing without tissue culture (Ali *et al.*, 2015; Yin *et al.*, 2015). Viral vectors for example tobacco rattle virus and Gemini viruses have been successfully used to carry out the delivery of guide RNAs into Cas- expressing plants which facilitates transient and high-throughput genome editing (Cody *et al.*, 2017). Virus-based delivery method is particularly beneficial for functional genomics and rapid trait evaluation; although, its limited cargo capacity, host specificity, and biosafety considerations restrict the opportunities of large-scale agricultural deployment (Liu *et al.*, 2021).

Table 9. Examples of virus made delivery systems using crisper

Crop	Target gene(s)	Delivery technique	Modified trait	Key results	Reference
Nicotiana benthamiana	<i>NbPDS</i>	TRV-gRNA and Cas9 plant	Albino phenotype	Structural editing	Ali et al., 2015
Tomato	<i>SLANT1</i>	Geminivirus-CRISPR	Anthocyanin accumulation	Visible phenotype	Baltes et al., 2014
Wheat	<i>TaGW2</i>	Barley stripe mosaic virus	Grain size	Virus directed editing	Hu et al., 2019
Arabidopsis	<i>AtCHL11</i>	TRV-CRISPR	Chlorophyll synthesis	Bleaching of leaf	Cody et al., 2017
Rice	<i>OsPDS</i>	Foxtail mosaic virus	Albino phenotype	High-throughput editing	Mei et al., 2019

11. DNA-free Editing (RNP Delivery)

DNA-free genome editing technique involves direct delivery of already assembled Cas protein–guide RNA ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complexes into plant cells. This approach resists stable integration of foreign DNA and reduces the risk of off-target effects associated with longer nuclease expression (Woo *et al.*, 2015; Svitashev *et al.*, 2016). RNPs can be delivered through protoplast transfection or particle bombardment into the embryos and calli, resulting in precise genome modifications that are indistinguishable from the naturally occurring mutations (Liang *et al.*, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Because of the absence of transgenic sequences, DNA-free edited plants are considered more acceptable under current regulatory frameworks in several countries (Chen *et al.*, 2019; Maher *et al.*, 2020).

Future Perspectives

The future of CRISPR–Cas technology in crop development is believed to move beyond simple gene knockouts and move toward highly precise and predictable genome modifications by which we can get high end results. Some emerging tools for example base editors and prime editors enable targeted nucleotide substitutions without even inducing double-strand breaks and thereby reducing unintended mutations and improving editing accuracy (Komor *et al.*, 2016; Anzalone *et al.*, 2019). These technologies are particularly precious for correcting single- nucleotide polymorphisms which associates with agronomically important traits such as yield, stress tolerance, and disease resistance. The refinement of such precision-editing platforms will make breeders capable to mimic naturally occurring alleles and accelerate trait introgression into elite cultivars (Zong *et al.*, 2017; Lin *et al.*, 2020). Another important future direction involves the development of multiplex and polygenic editing strategies. Many agronomic traits such as drought tolerance and yield stability, are controlled by complex gene networks rather than single genes. Advances in multiplex CRISPR systems will provide the capability of simultaneous targeting of multiple genes or regulatory regions within a single transformation event (Ma *et al.*, 2015; Wang *et al.*, 2018). This capability facilitates trait stacking and coordinated regulation of whole pathway which is essential for engineering crops adapted to changing climatic conditions and anthropogenic adverse climates. Enhanced guide RNA design algorithms and machine-learning-based prediction tools are also believed to enhance editing efficiency and minimise off-target activity (Haeussler *et al.*, 2016; Listgarten *et al.*, 2018). Epigenome editing represents another favorable frontier in crop biotechnology. By using catalytically inactive Cas proteins (dCas) fused with specific transcriptional activators, repressors, or chromatin-modifying enzymes, gene expression can be modulated without altering the underlying DNA sequence (Hilton *et al.*, 2015; Gallego-Bartolomé *et al.*, 2018). This approach ensures reversible and environmentally responsive control of agronomic traits such as flowering time and stress-responsive gene expression. Epigenome editing may also facilitate the study and exploitation of heritable epigenetic variation in crops which can provide a novel dimension to plant breeding (Kearns *et al.*, 2015). From an agricultural sustainability perspective the CRISPR–Cas systems are expected to contribute substantially to the development of climate-resilient and resource-efficient crops with desired nutritional qualities. Editing of genes for water-use efficiency, nitrogen-use efficiency, and photosynthetic performance offers potential solutions to food security challenges under global climate change (Scheben *et al.*, 2017; Rodríguez-Leal *et al.*, 2017). This integration of CRISPR technology with specific genomic selection, speed breeding, and high-throughput phenotyping will further shorten breeding cycles and enhance crop adaptability for desired results (Varshney *et al.*, 2019).

Conclusion

CRISPR–Cas technology has emerged as a huge transformative tool for crop improvement by enabling precise, efficient, and programmable modification of plant genomes to get desired products both quantitatively and qualitatively. When we compared this technique with conventional breeding and earlier genetic engineering approaches, CRISPR-based genome editing techniques offers unprecedented accuracy and stability in manipulating genes

associated with yield, stress tolerance, disease resistance, and improved nutritional quality (Chen *et al.*, 2019; Scheben *et al.*, 2017). The availability of diverse CRISPR systems for example Cas9, Cas12, and Cas13, has even more expanded the range of editable targets from DNA to RNA, due to which the broadening the functional scope of genome engineering in plants can be seen (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Significant and valuable progress has been made in the development of delivery strategies for CRISPR system components including Agrobacterium- mediated transformation, particle bombardment, protoplast transfection, virus-based delivery, and DNA-free ribonucleoprotein approaches (Altpeter *et al.*, 2016; Liu *et al.*, 2021). These tools or approaches have enabled the generation of both transgenic and transgene-free edited crops, with the latter getting increasing importance due to regulatory and public acceptance considerations (Woo *et al.*, 2015; Maher *et al.*, 2020). Nevertheless, but the technical challenges related to transformation efficiency, plant regeneration, and off-target effects remain significant barriers which is particularly for recalcitrant crop species (Haeussler *et al.*, 2016; Svitashv *et al.*, 2016). The application and function of CRISPR–Cas systems have already demonstrated substantial potential in introducing agronomically important traits such as drought tolerance, pathogen resistance, herbicide tolerance, and enhanced nutritional value (Rodríguez-Leal *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2018). Multiplex genome editing and pathway-level techniques also allow the manipulation of complex quantitative traits which offers solutions to challenges posed by climate change and global food insecurity and rising populations with rising demands (Ma *et al.*, 2015; Varshney *et al.*, 2019). Some in this field of emerging technologies such as base editing, prime editing, and epigenome editing are expected to enable more subtle and predictable desired genetic modifications which closely resembles natural allelic variation (Komor *et al.*, 2016; Anzalone *et al.*, 2019; Hilton *et al.*, 2015). From a regulatory and socio- economic perspective we can even say that the distinction between transgenic and genome- edited crops continues to influence the momentum of CRISPR adoption in agriculture (Chen *et al.*, 2019). Coordination and alignment of regulatory frameworks, coupled with transparent risk assessment and public engagement, will be essential for understanding the full benefits of this technology. Integration of CRISPR–Cas systems with genomics-assisted breeding along with speed breeding, and high-throughput phenotyping is likely to further increase the development of climate-resilient and resource-efficient crops (Scheben *et al.*, 2017; Varshney *et al.*, 2019). Overall, CRISPR–Cas technology shows a paradigm shift in crop biotechnology which is bridging the gap between classical breeding and modern molecular genetic editing technologies. Continued innovation and enhancement in editing precision, delivery systems, and regulatory alignment will be very important to ensure that CRISPR-derived crops can successfully contribute to sustainable agriculture and global food security. CRISPR–Cas- based genome editing system has redefined crop improvement strategies through enabling precise, rapid, and versatile genetic modifications. However, the successful agricultural deployment will depend on advancements in delivery technologies their smart use along with reduction of off-target effects, and development of supportive regulatory frameworks.

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